

1 *In situ* calibration of a tube passive sampler in wastewater
2 effluent with adjustable volumetric flow for assessment of
3 micro-pollutants with fluctuating concentrations

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15

16 **Abstract**

17 We present a versatile flow-through tube passive sampling device (TPS), with
18 controllable feed water volumetric flow, that can be calibrated *in situ* against the feed
19 water load of organic micro-pollutants (OMPs). This semi-passive approach has the
20 advantage of a determinable water load feeding the sampling device. The design of
21 the TPS allows for new sampling scenarios in closed piping while providing stable and

22 controlled sampling conditions. The calibration referencing an OMP's feed water load
23 can describe the uptake behavior from wastewater treatment plant effluent with
24 potentially highly fluctuating OMP concentrations. The TPS and its load-dependent
25 calibration under realistic environmental conditions proves possible for a variety of
26 organic trace substances in a challenging matrix. Nine of the 20 monitored
27 representative OMPs could be calibrated load-dependently, leading to a good
28 agreement between the calculated concentration from the TPS and the average
29 concentration of corresponding direct measurements. Due to the simple measuring
30 principle and the membrane-less discs, many influencing factors such as diffusion,
31 turbulence and lag time phenomena can be neglected. The TPS could support the
32 existing online measurement analytics in a (process-) water treatment plant by
33 delivering integrated water concentrations for discharge monitoring.

34 **Keywords**

35 passive sampling, load dependent calibration, wastewater, organic contaminants,
36 fluctuating concentrations, organic micro-pollutants, flow-through.

37 **Synopsis**

38 The study introduces a versatile tube passive sampling device that allows controlled
39 flow and *in situ* calibration for monitoring organic micro-pollutants in wastewater,
40 demonstrating effective load-dependent calibration under fluctuating conditions.

41 **Contribution**

42 **T. Hensel:** methodology, investigation, software and writing original draft, **J.-H. Hein:**
43 methodology, investigation and software, **T. Reemtsma:** writing - review, **A. Sperlich:**
44 project administration, **R. Gnirß:** funding acquisition, **F. Zietzschmann:** methodology,
45 supervision, review & editing.

46 1 Introduction

47 Organic micro-pollutants (OMP) play a central role in the quality assessment of various
48 compartments of the water cycle; wastewater in particular accounts for a high
49 proportion of the introduction of OMPs into water bodies¹. Particularly in highly
50 urbanised areas, it is necessary to consider not only the concentration of these
51 substances but also the associated load which the aquatic environment is confronted
52 with²⁻⁵.

53 Several options for wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) effluent monitoring exist:

- 54 • Grab samples which provide accurate snapshots for monitoring but lack any
55 information outside the individual sampled point in time⁶,
- 56 • composite samples which provide average data over the chosen time period but
57 require costly and laborious continuous maintenance and surveillance,
- 58 • passive samplers (PS) which provide cheap and readily available qualitative time-
59 integrative data over the application period but tend to loose accuracy if OMP
60 concentrations vary substantially^{7,8}.

61 The principle of PS is the enrichment of analytes from a donor phase (typically liquids
62 like aqueous phases; or gases⁹) onto a sorbent and subsequent analysis of the
63 sorbent for sorbed analytes after a certain period. PS-enriched OMP for subsequent
64 analysis should be neither degradable nor volatile. There is a variety of passive
65 sampler types for aqueous use, specializing in the type of contaminants they are
66 targeting, like the well-described membrane-encapsulated sampler “polar organic
67 chemical integrative sampler” (POCIS)¹⁰ or the organic-diffusive gradients in thin-films
68 (o-DGT)¹¹ that are targeting polar organic compounds. There are also approaches that
69 assess viruses¹², use different materials like silicone rubber¹³, apply tube shaped

70 devices¹⁴, or try more complex devices with a forced flow through^{15,16}. To date, the
71 passive samplers described in the literature are limited with respect to possible points
72 of uses. For example, passive sampler-based monitoring of wastewater streams
73 requires non-pressurized, free-flowing, accessible sampling locations^{17,18} like ponds,
74 basins, streams etc. In addition, many approaches use laboratory-based calibration,
75 thus potentially missing important environmental factors¹⁹. In drinking and ground
76 water (with relatively stable OMP concentrations), the concentration statements of per-
77 and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) from POCIS with laboratory flow-through
78 calibration led to a good agreement to the accompanied composite samples²⁰. In
79 surface water, quantitative applications of laboratory-calibrated PS appear
80 controversial, leading to only qualitative statements²¹. Applications in wastewater
81 introduce an extremely inhomogeneous and challenging matrix²² compared to
82 drinking, ground, or surface water. Laboratory PS calibration under controlled
83 conditions cannot provide sufficient reliability for such highly complex water matrices
84 of strong compositional fluctuations. Known impacts on the OMP-uptake like salinity,
85 temperature²³, pH value, and the concentration of dissolved organic matter (DOC)²⁴,
86 all of which can change rapidly, are mostly neglected. For these reasons, *in situ*
87 calibration is much more accurate²⁵ and leads to good quantitative statements in
88 wastewater with passive sampler applications (for OMPs with non-fluctuating
89 concentrations)⁸. However most passive sampling devices are calibrated *in vitro* in
90 their kinetic uptake phase²⁶.

91 To compensate for changing peripheral parameters (temperature, turbulence, etc.),
92 isotope-labelled performance reference compounds (PRC) can be used²⁷. The use of
93 PRCs though has its limitations (e.g. different release behaviour of PRC as compared
94 to uptake behaviour of target OMP)^{28,29}.

95 Many authors commonly avoid the use of PRCs and rely on *in situ* calibration^{30–32},
96 obviating the need for PRCs, whereas all influences on the uptake are present.^{33,34}
97 The present study compares an *in situ* time-dependent calibration with a load-
98 dependent approach which relates the uptake of analytes into the sorbent to the feed
99 water load of a substance to the PS. With this new calibration approach the goals of
100 this study are:

- 101 • Introduce a controlled flow-through sampling device (tube passive sampler,
102 TPS) that has an adjustable feed water flow,
- 103 • present a quantitative load-dependent calibration approach for 20 organic micro
104 pollutants (OMPs) from WWTP effluent,
- 105 • compare the concentration results of 11 OMPs derived by the presented TPS
106 to OMP concentrations from conventional composite sampling in a WWTP
107 effluent.

108 2 Materials and Methods

109 2.1 *Design of the Tube Passive Sampler*

110 The design of the TPS (cf. Fig. 1) aims at highly controllable and reproducible sorption
111 of OMPs onto PS discs, suppressing influences like turbulence²⁷, flow velocities³⁵,
112 additional membranes¹⁰, and avoiding PRCs³⁶. The TPS can access open water
113 surfaces by use of a gear pump. The design also allows to conveniently sample in
114 pressurised lines by enclosing the sorption discs in a special designed pipe (Fig. 1C),
115 thus in any monitoring setup that uses slight over pressure as found in treatment
116 plants, process tubing, or pumping stations; in such scenarios, an active pump is not
117 necessary.

118

119 **Fig. 1:** **A:** Schematic cross-section and zig-zag-flow diagram of the miniaturised TPS. Circles with dots facing
 120 towards, circles with crosses facing away. **B:** Photograph of the TPS. **C:** Integration into a process water system.

121 Within the TPS, a constant sample water flow passes laterally along the passive
 122 sampling discs (Fig. 1A and Fig. S6A, including TPS & housing dimensions). A mass
 123 flow controller (MFC) sets the volume flow for each experiment. The device consists
 124 of stainless steel and was designed and constructed by GCI GmbH Königs
 125 Wusterhausen (GER), patent DE 10 2016 003 8430, 2017. Four different commercially
 126 available and unmodified 47 mm-discs were used for evaluation (Atlantic® HLB
 127 (Biotage), Atlantic® DVB (Biotage), Atlantic® C18 (Biotage) and Resprep-C18
 128 (Restek)). All discs came with glass fibre layers applied by the manufacturers. The
 129 stainless steel disc retainer fits the diameter of the discs as well as the thickness
 130 (5 mm) of the discs exactly and holds the discs with a stainless steel mesh-plate (mesh
 131 diameter ca. 7 mm) on both exposed sides (for more details see Fig. S6B), leaving
 132 1735 mm² disc area per side exposed to the sample water.

133 2.2 Calculation of the load-dependent calibration of the tube passive sampler

134 Our TPS calibration bases on the classical time-dependent calibration approach
135 discussed in detail by Booij et al.²⁶, cf. equation (1) below, and applied in a variety of
136 studies^{8,16}, with constant concentrations. This approach proved only sparsely
137 applicable on OMPs with strongly fluctuating concentrations^{8,26}. It uses a time-
138 weighted average concentration ($c_{w,twa}$) and follows equation (1).

$$M_{D,time}(t) = R_S * \int c_W dt \quad (1)$$

139 $M_{D,time}$ (g) is the amount of analyte on the disc after the exposure time t (d), R_S
140 represents the sampling rate in the dimension of ($L * d^{-1}$), $\int c_W dt = t * c_{W,TWA}$.

141 To differentiate between the time-dependent and the load-dependent calibration we
142 introduce the collection ratio (R_C , dimensionless), related to the sampling rate through
143 equation (2)

$$R_S = R_C * Q \quad (2)$$

144 with Q being the (adjustable) fixed water flow through the sampler.

145 This difference allows the calculation of the TPS's feed water load $M_{W,cum}$ via equation
146 (3).

$$M_{W,cum}(t) = Q * \int c_W dt \quad (3)$$

147 Using equations (2) and (3) in equation (1) leads to equation (4) to calculate the
148 compound-specific collection ratio R_C .

$$R_C = \frac{M_D(t)}{M_{W,cum}(t)} \quad (4)$$

149 To calculate the time weighted average concentration $c_{W,TWA}$ from the sampling ratio
150 R_C , equations (1) and (2) can be combined to equation (5).

$$c_{W,TWA} = \frac{M_D(t)}{R_C * t * Q} \quad (5)$$

151 2.3 *Experimental design*

152 Evaluation and *in situ* calibration of the TPS took place in a WWTP treating domestic
153 wastewater with some industrial wastewater shares in Berlin, Germany. The WWTP
154 has a capacity of 42 500 m³ per day which is equivalent to a population equivalent of
155 ~350 000. The TPS was placed inside the process monitoring station at the WWTP
156 outlet channel. Branching from a pressurized effluent pipe with continuous flow inside
157 the station, two overflow containers were fed with moderate overpressure (~1.2 bar),
158 for the setup see Fig. S2. For the calibration experiments, an automatic water sampler
159 WS Porti 24T (WaterSam GmbH, Balingen, Germany) was placed just outside the
160 monitoring station. The sampler rinsed its hose automatically before it took
161 consecutive 8 hour composite samples (20 mL/6 min) of the effluent throughout each
162 complete experiment. The samples were cooled at 4 °C until transfer to the laboratory.
163 All passive sampling experiments took place consecutively one after another, all
164 accompanied with their individual composite samples. For the order and duration of
165 the TPS experiments, see Fig. S7.

166 2.4 *Preparation of the sorption discs*

167 Disc conditioning involved careful placement of the DVB and HLB sorption discs in a
168 solid phase extraction (SPE) disc manifold, followed by rinsing with LC-MS-grade
169 solutions of 5 mL methanol with 1 % (v/v) formic acid, 5 mL methanol, 5 mL of methanol
170 with 1 % (v/v) ammonia and 20 mL ultra-pure water before storage in ultra-pure water
171 until usage. Mounting of the discs within the TPS comprised careful fixation into the
172 disc retainer, insertion of the disc retainer into the TPS, and closing of the lids. The

173 mass flow controller of the electronic control unit yielded a steady volumetric water
174 flow through the TPS. After the experiment, short rinsing with ultra-pure water removed
175 deposits and particles on the discs (while inside the retainer), followed by
176 disassemblage of the retainers and transfer of the discs into a polypropylene box lined
177 with a sheet of aluminium foil for transportation. In the laboratory, the discs dried under
178 a gentle airflow in a fume hood for 2 days. The discs were then transferred in an SPE
179 disc manifold and were rinsed consecutively with 5 mL of methanol with 1 % (v/v)
180 formic acid, 5 mL methanol, 5 mL of methanol with 1 % (v/v) ammonia collecting all
181 three filtrates of one disc in one vial. The combined filtrates were concentrated to 0.5
182 mL in a water bath under a constant nitrogen flow, transferred in a 1.5 mL-vial and
183 reconstituted with methanol to 1 mL. The vials were stored at -25 °C. Each disc
184 represented an individual sample.

185 *2.5 Analysis*

186 Eluates were measured in aqueous dilutions of 1:500 and 1:50.000, water samples in
187 aqueous dilutions of 1:5 and 1:100, respectively. The compounds were analysed using
188 an Exactive+ Orbitrap system with Dionex eluent pumps from Thermo Fisher Scientific
189 (Waltham, USA). The injection volume onto the online SPE column (Thermo Fisher
190 Scientific Hypersil GOLD aQ 2.1x20 mm) was 1 mL. The analytical column was an
191 Acquity UPLC HSS T3 (2.1x50 mm, 1.8 µm, Waters Corp., Milford USA). Compound
192 separation resulted from a constant flow of 0.6 mL per minute, using a binary eluent
193 gradient of ultra-pure water (1 % (v/v) methanol, 0.1 % (v/v) formic acid) (A) and
194 methanol (0.1 % (v/v) formic acid) (B) with a gradient elution from 1 % B ramping
195 linearly to 95 % B at 7 minutes. Column rinsing uses 99 % B for 2.5 minutes, followed
196 by a reconstitution step on starting conditions at 1 % B for 3 minutes. Ionisation was
197 achieved using an electron spray ionisation (ESI) in positive and negative mode. The

198 Orbitrap mass spectrometer was calibrated every day leading to an accuracy of ≤ 5
199 ppm. The calibration curves ranged from 0.01 $\mu\text{g/L}$ to 1 $\mu\text{g/L}$ of the calibration standard
200 (for each respective compound), using internal calibration with isotope-labelled
201 standards added to all samples and calibration levels, respectively, see Tab. S1 and
202 Section S1. The evaluation of any blind value of the TPS or the discs themselves was
203 negative; for more details, see Section S2.

204 3 Results and Discussion

205 For optimization, we did preliminary tests to identify the best disc material and the most
206 suitable volume flow (section 3.1). We then performed a proof of principle experiment
207 for 20 OMPs with a first (larger) TPS prototype (section 3.2). In the next step, we
208 installed and calibrated the final (mini) TPS prototype in the WWTP (section 3.3). An
209 Evaluation of the mini TPS capabilities for quantitative OMP concentration inference
210 in the WWTP follows in section 3.4.

211 3.1 *Preliminary experiments*

212 **WWTP effluent characterization and OMP concentrations**

213 The concentrations of the OMPs metoprolol and tolyltriazole, together with chemical
214 oxygen demand (COD), as an indicator for overall organic WWTP effluent content,
215 and temperature over a 28-day period (spring 2022) are shown in Fig. 2. While
216 tolyltriazole concentrations fluctuate profoundly during the observational period
217 (between 3 - 13 $\mu\text{g/L}$), metoprolol concentrations vary far less (2 - 3 $\mu\text{g/L}$) with almost
218 no abrupt changes. In the case of tolyltriazole, a potential weekly pattern seems
219 discernible but intra-weekly variation is still strong. Tolyltriazole can serve as a proxy
220 for other OMPs with fluctuating concentrations (e.g. benzotriazole) while metoprolol
221 resembles other OMPs with relatively constant concentrations (e.g. phenazone,

222 DEET). For reasons of clarity, we use tolyltriazole and metoprolol as exemplary OMPs
 223 throughout the document if not stated otherwise. With average values for COD of
 224 40 mg/L, NO_3^- of 8.3 mg/L, NH_4^+ of 0.3 mg/L, PO_4^{3-} of 0.7 mg/L, TSS of 4.3 mg/L, the
 225 examined WWTP effluent indicates an overall high wastewater treatment efficiency
 226 with high refractive background organic levels (DOC of ~13 mg/L).

227
 228 **Fig. 2:** Concentrations (squares) from 8-hour-composite samples of tolyltriazole (black) and metoprolol (grey) in
 229 WWTP effluent during a 28 day period, from 01 march 2022 till 29 march 2022, Mondays are marked with red lines;
 230 chemical oxygen demand (COD, triangles) and temperature (circles) derived from online measurements.

231 **Passive sampler disc material selection**

232 To find SPE discs that were durable and would extract the selected compounds from
 233 the wastewater matrix, we exposed four commercially available SPE discs to WWTP
 234 effluent in a closed beaker on a lab shaker for 24 h and analyzed their extracts. In
 235 addition to the relative uptake of the selected compounds (shown in Fig. S3), we
 236 assessed the texture and handling of the discs before and after exposure. Among all
 237 tested discs, the Biotage Atlantic® discs with the sorption materials divinylbenzene
 238 (DVB) and a reversed-phase sorbent (hydrophilic-lipophilic-balanced, HLB) were able
 239 to collect most of the compounds from the matrix. Both materials were tested in the
 240 first prototype of the TPS. After several experiments with time periods greater than two

241 days, the HLB-discs tend to disintegrate as opposed to the DVB discs whose external
242 glass fibre layer provides for mechanical protection.

243 For a more detailed assessment of the OMP capture capabilities of HLB and DVB
244 discs, we equipped two large TPS with four HLB-discs and four DVB-discs,
245 respectively, and fed the same effluent stream at the exact same conditions
246 (temperature, pH, etc.) during five consecutive 48 h experiments with varying flow
247 rates (20 to 100 L/h). OMPs like acesulfame, 4-dimethylaminoantipyrine,
248 dimethylpyrazolone, triphenylphosphate, and propyphenazone remained undetected
249 on any of the discs. Interestingly, the two materials (DVB and HLB) collected the same
250 14 compounds in similar amounts. For further experiments, we decided to use DVB
251 discs, because of their higher physical integrity and better market availability. The
252 normalized uptake, or ratio between the OMP-load on the disc and the OMP feed water
253 load, of the 14 compounds for both materials in each experiment is shown in Fig. S4.

254 **Volumetric flow optimization**

255 We evaluated the influence of the volumetric flow on the OMP disc uptake by varying
256 flows at 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 L/h in consecutive 48 hours experiments. The
257 simultaneously running auto sampler continuously took 2-hour-composite samples,
258 allowing for the calculation of the OMP feed water loads. The absolute disc uptakes
259 with metoprolol and tolyltriazole, respectively, relate differently to increasing volumetric
260 flows through the TPS (Fig. 3A & B, boxplots). For metoprolol, doubling, tripling etc. of
261 the volumetric flow does only increase disc uptakes very weakly. The absolute
262 tolyltriazole uptake at volumetric flows between 20 - 80 L/h ranged between
263 0.4 - 0.7 µg/disc, with no clear discernible trend. Only for the highest tested volumetric
264 flow of 100 L/h, higher absolute disc loads occurred, roughly double that of the other
265 flows. As the experimental design required consecutive tests of different volumetric

266 flows, temporal concentration variations of an OMP in the feed water resulted in
 267 non-linear OMP feed water loads for tolyltriazole (cf. Fig. 2) while for metoprolol, nearly
 268 constant feed water concentrations resulted in a largely linear trend of the feed water
 269 load. Fig. 3C shows the normalised disc uptake as a quotient of the absolute disc
 270 uptake by the corresponding OMP feed water load.

271

272 **Fig. 3: A and B:** OMP uptake onto DVB discs in TPS over two days of exposure (left y-axes, box-and-whisker
 273 plots) and feed water loads (right y-axes, triangle & square symbols) at different volume flows as box plots for
 274 metoprolol (A) and tolyltriazole (B). **C:** Normalised uptake (OMP uptake divided by feed water load) over tested
 275 volumetric flow rates. Note that experiments ran consecutively (not in parallel).

276 The normalised uptake decreases with increasing volume flow for both compounds,
 277 approaching a merely constant value between 0.01 - 0.02 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$, similarly observable
 278 for the other tested 14 OMPs at levels of 0.01 - 0.16 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ (cf. Fig. S4). This
 279 normalized depiction of the passive sampler OMP disc uptake, relative to the OMP
 280 feed water load, demonstrates that low volumetric flows result in the highest passive-
 281 sampled percentage of OMPs fed to the TPS.

282 The effect of the volume flow on the *absolute* uptake of the passive sampler is clearly
 283 influenced by the OMP feed water load as both examples show. The low impact of the

284 water flow on the *relative* uptake (for vol. flows >40 L/h in the TPS) corresponds with
285 uptake experiments of pharmaceuticals on POCIS passive samplers in specially
286 designed effluent canals of a Swiss WWTP¹⁷. However, the flow seems to have an
287 influence on biofouling and particulate depositions as well as the experiment duration
288 (cf. Fig. S1), especially pronounced at higher ambient temperatures. These findings
289 led to the decision to use a volume flow of 40 L/h to ensure a balance between a low
290 and consistent uptake while maintaining enough flow to keep the biofouling on the
291 sorption discs to a minimum.

292 3.2 *In situ calibration of the tube passive sampler*

293 In the top panels of Fig. 4A and B, the uptakes of metoprolol (left) and tolyltriazole
294 (right) are plotted over the time of exposure, following the time-dependent approach
295 of calibration²⁶. For both substances, a linear increase of the uptake over time is
296 discernible. The uptake did not increase further in the experiments with exposure times
297 of 21 and 28 days, respectively, compared to 14 d, indicating maximal uptake (likely
298 constituted as a dynamic equilibrium between sample water and disc). The increasing
299 biofilm and particle deposition (cf. Fig. S1), impacting OMP mass transfer to/from the
300 passive sampler discs, may explain the greater errors in disc uptake with increasing
301 experiment duration for metoprolol^{7,37} as noticeable in Fig. 4A and C.

302 For the calibration, we calculated a threshold disc load at 2/3 of the maximum disc
303 load at 14 days, similar to Huckins et al.⁷. With respect to the linearity beyond the
304 typically discussed “half-life”-sampler uptake, we decided to set the threshold to 2/3 of
305 the uptake. For later experiments, the threshold can be translated to the maximum
306 exposure time of the individual OMP. All values below this threshold were used for an
307 unweighted linear regression with no intercept. The regression did not include values
308 from the 14, 21, and 28 days experiments, since disc uptakes at these durations

309 exceed the defined threshold. We conducted two instances of the 2- and 7-day
310 exposure experiments (note that this does not increase the number of values of the
311 independent variable (time, x-axis) for the time-dependent plots (Fig. 4 top)).

312

313 **Fig. 4: Top:** metoprolol (A) and tolyltriazole (B) amounts on disc of the large TPS over exposure time in experiments
314 of variable durations (2, 7, 14, 21, 28 days) and **bottom:** Same amounts on disc of metoprolol (C) and tolyltriazole
315 (D) over feed water loads (as obtained from continuous 8 h composite autosampler values) through the TPS during
316 the corresponding experimental run times; with linear regression, forced through origin, (dashed lines) and
317 thresholds at 2/3 of respective maximum disc uptakes (grey lines); red arrows linking same values in the different
318 depiction approaches; 2 and 7 day experiments conducted in consecutive duplicates. Datapoints result from means
319 of four replicates.

320 The TPS design provides highly controlled conditions, especially with respect to the
321 volumetric flow, thus allowing to precisely calculate the OMP feed water load during
322 each experiment. Using the OMP feed water load data directly links the measured disc
323 uptake to the OMP amount passed through the TPS. The resulting
324 calibration/regression line is independent of the experimental runtime in the way that
325 similar OMP feed water loads may occur during shorter times (when the OMP
326 concentration in the feed water is higher) or during longer times (when the OMP
327 concentration in the feed water is lower). For compounds that have a relatively

328 constant concentration over time like metoprolol, the load values show a similar x-axis
329 distribution compared to the time-dependent graph, despite different axis units (arrows
330 from A to C). Nonetheless, even small differences in concentration among the
331 consecutively conducted experiments of the same exposure time lead to different
332 loads, thus small shifts on the x-axis (Fig. 4C). When considering a compound with
333 highly variable concentrations, like tolyltriazole, the load-dependent calibration (Fig.
334 4D) demonstrates pronounced differences as compared to the time-dependent
335 calibration (Fig. 4B): The 4 arrows to the left of the graph (from Fig. 4 B to D) depict
336 the splitting of each of the two consecutive experiments with 2 and 7 days exposure.
337 The concentration variations of tolyltriazole result in different feed water loads in
338 experiments that had the same duration (2 days or 7 days) but were conducted at
339 different times (i.e. at different feed water concentrations). This observation also
340 occurs for the other observed OMPs' calibration curves, see Fig. S8.

341 Within Fig. 4, panels B & D, the two rightmost arrows indicate a lower tolyltriazole disc
342 uptake during the 21 days experiment compared to the 14 days experiment. While the
343 time-dependent calibration leads to the conclusion that the 14 day experiment marks
344 the maximum allowable exposure time (corresponding to the highest OMP disc
345 uptake), the feed water load-dependent calibration demonstrates that longer exposure
346 times are possible – with almost linear increases of the disc uptake up until the 21st
347 day (despite not integrated in the calibration due to our conservative 2/3 threshold
348 approach). This behavior applies to other substances whose concentrations fluctuate,
349 like industrial chemical benzotriazole (data not shown). Compounds that have a mostly
350 constant concentration over time (e.g. metoprolol) show no comparable change in data
351 point sequence (on the x-axis) when plotted over the load, although a spreading of
352 x-axis values occurs in the load-dependent plot (cf. other calibration plots, e.g. AMPH

353 and DEET in Fig. S8). The plotting of disc-load/ $c_{W,TWA}^{8,26}$ vs. time, rearranges the data
354 points on the y-axis depending on their specific $c_{W,TWA}$ values, which influences the
355 linear regression, cf. Fig S10. The load-dependent representation provides a
356 resolution of each individual experiment according to its specific measured load.

357 The feed water load-dependent calibration is powerful in scenarios of largely varying
358 OMP concentrations – such as WWTP effluents with hourly, daily, weekly, monthly etc.
359 patterns of industrial/household chemicals or pharmaceutical agents (Fig. 2; and
360 weekly variation of x-ray contrast media^{38,39}). In cases of substantially fluctuating OMP
361 concentrations, the disc uptake might occur rapidly (high OMP concentrations, cf.
362 tolyltriazole 14 d experiment in Fig. 4) or slowly (low OMP concentrations, cf.
363 tolyltriazole 21 d experiment). Note that the 14 d experiment and the 21 d experiment
364 were *not* executed in parallel but consecutively. Hence, not the exposure time is
365 generally the limiting variable, but the maximum disc uptake is the limiting variable.
366 Resulting from defined time values in time-dependent calibration approaches, the
367 corresponding models include fewer x-axis values than the feed water load-dependent
368 approach (cf. differentiation of data points when changing from top graphs to bottom
369 graphs in Fig. 4). Passive samplers of “classical” designs – thus lacking the highly
370 controlled characteristics of the here-presented TPS – additionally suffer from
371 uncertainties induced by either unknown or fluctuating volumetric flows. Such cases
372 occur when deploying passive samplers freely into water streams in ponds/basins etc.

373 For some OMPs (acesulfame, propyphenazone, 4-dimethylaminoantipyrine, iomeprol,
374 tributylphosphate, tris-(2-chloroisopropyl)-phosphate, triphenylphosphate), an
375 evaluation was not possible due to a lack of data from the water samples. For valsartan
376 acid however, a special behavior occurs: This OMP occurs continuously in all aqueous
377 samples and also on all PS discs but the application of both the time-dependent and

378 the load-dependent calibration fails, see Fig. S9. This behavior could result from
379 (microbial) transformation of valsartan and other sartans into valsartan acid,
380 accumulating not only from the feed water but also being formed directly in the passive
381 sampler from precursors^{40,41}. Unstable and/or potentially degradable substances are
382 therefore not suitable for assessments via passive sampling. For
383 2-methylthiobenzothiazole (MTBT), no calibration was possible, potentially due to the
384 volatility of this thioether and long dwell time on the sampling disc.

385 The classical sampling rate (R_S in L/d) and here-introduced collection ratio (R_C with no
386 dimension) for all evaluable OMPs are summarized in Tab. 1 under “large prototype”.
387 The sampling rates (R_S) and collection ratios (R_C) result from the slope of the
388 respective linear regression and for R_S the mean concentration over all experiments
389 included in the linear regression corresponding to Fig. 4. The units of R_C allow for
390 direct inference of the amount of an OMP collected from the feed water flow to the
391 TPS. Since the coefficient of determination will not give an adequate interpretation on
392 the error of the used no-intercept regressions used to determine R_S and R_C ⁴², we use
393 the absolute residual error (ARE, in mg) of the disc uptake (y-values) to interpret the
394 quality of fit, see also Section S3. For the large prototype, 7 of the 11 OMPs ARE are
395 comparable if not better for the load-dependent calibration than for time-dependent
396 one (highlighted in green). Note that both the time-dependent and the load-dependent
397 calibration use the benefits of the TPS (flow-through device, steady flow conditions,
398 constant temperature). Furthermore, we used consecutive experiments, which differs
399 from other studies that start different experiments at the same time and only vary the
400 exposure length⁸. Future studies should assess the TPS’ benefits (load-dependent
401 calibration, time-dependent calibration) against classical passive sampling without

402 volumetric flow control (e.g., POCIS, o-DGT) with corresponding time-dependent
 403 calibration.

404 **Tab. 1:** Performance parameters (sampling rate R_S and collection ratio R_C) of the *in situ* calibration of the two TPS,
 405 better performing calibration according to absolute residual error highlighted in green; ARE: Absolute residual error
 406 (ARE compares modelled and measured disc uptake data points, see section S3).

Compound	Large prototype				Miniaturised prototype			
	Time-Dependent		Load-Dependent		Time-Dependent		Load-Dependent	
	R_S (mL/d)	ARE (mg)	R_C (ng/ μ g)	ARE (mg)	R_S (mL/d)	ARE (mg)	R_C (ng/ μ g)	ARE (mg)
Phenazone	29	0.017	0.035	0.01	38	0.058	0.094	0.053
AAA	13	0.21	0.014	0.18	37	0.33	0.075	0.25
AMPH	19	0.028	0.016	0.031	30	0.069	0.077	0.069
FAA	27	0.28	0.026	0.38	35	1.10	0.075	0.99
Diclofenac	40	0.045	0.039	0.054	46	0.36	0.097	0.44
Metoprolol	43	0.063	0.043	0.044	33	0.11	0.071	0.15
lomeprol	21	0.33	0.014	0.24				
Valsartan	37	1.1	0.023	0.39				
DEET	39	0.008	0.047	0.006	32	0.017	0.082	0.011
Benzotriazole	13	1.70	0.023	0.92	15	0.58	0.037	0.48
Tolyltriazole	34	0.18	0.037	0.23	44	1.0	0.104	0.88

407

408 3.3 Miniaturisation and integration in online measurement

409 One of the goals of this study was to miniaturize the TPS in a way that it could be used
 410 permanently side-by-side existing monitoring equipment in WWTPs, whilst reducing
 411 the number of deployable passive sampler discs to two. We conducted consecutive
 412 experiments with the miniaturized TPS prototype at exposure times of 3, 4, 5, 7, 8 and
 413 14 days, now receiving WWTP effluent as feed water directly from a pressurized
 414 bypass of the online measurement devices in the monitoring station of the examined

415 WWTP. The experiments lasted ≤ 14 d due to the insight of the previous experiments
416 that $2/3$ of the maximum disc uptake generally occurred during that time. Again, the
417 subsequent calibration calculations only used data points below the $2/3$ threshold of
418 the observed maximum disc uptake.

419 The *in situ* time-dependent (top) and load-dependent (bottom) calibration plots of the
420 miniaturized TPS (mini TPS) are shown in Fig. 5. The comparison of the time-
421 dependent and the load-dependent calibrations for metoprolol (Fig. 5 A and C) shows
422 no particular change in order on the x-axis, as indicated by the arrows. In contrast, the
423 tolyltriazole data (Fig. 5 B and D) rearrange on the x-axis upon plotting load-
424 dependently (Fig. 5 B) opposed to time-dependent (Fig. 5 B). This behavior is similar
425 to the plots of tolyltriazole in the large TPS (Fig. 4 B and D). Such behavior also applies
426 to the calibration plots of diclofenac, benzotriazole, and AMPH, see Fig. S5, which also
427 contains the data for the other tested OMPs. When plotting disc-load/ $c_{w,TWA}$ vs. time,
428 a data point shift is observed on the y-axis, see Fig. S11. The re-arrangement of disc-
429 uptake data points demonstrates the importance of considering potentially variable
430 OMP concentrations. Even if a given OMP typically exhibits relatively constant
431 concentrations, potential variations may still occur, necessitating *in situ* calibration with
432 continuous monitoring of the OMP concentration. The R_C as well as the R_S results of
433 the corresponding calibrations are summarized in Tab. 1 under “miniaturized
434 prototype”.

435

436 **Fig. 5: Top:** Metoprolol (A) and tolyltriazole (B) amounts on disc of the miniaturized TPS over exposure time in
 437 experiments of variable durations (3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 14 days) and **bottom:** Same amounts on disc over metoprolol (C)
 438 and tolyltriazole (D) feed water loads (as obtained from continuous 24 h composite samples) through the mini-TPS
 439 during the corresponding experimental run times; regressions only including values below threshold; red arrows
 440 linking same values in the different graphs. Data points result from means of duplicates.

441 3.4 Validation of the tube passive sampler

442 In order to test the load-dependent calibration (Fig. 5 C and D), we carried out an
 443 additional 7-day test (we chose this experimental run time so that the disc uptake
 444 would likely not exceed the threshold and thus lie within the calibration range). We
 445 used the measured disc uptake from this experiment to calculate the feed water load
 446 resulting from the linear regression equation in Fig. 5. Accompanying continuous
 447 composite samples provided the necessary information on the actual concentrations
 448 in the feed water during the experiment as a reference. The calculation results using
 449 R_C along with equation (5), the results using R_S and the results from the composite
 450 samples are compared in Tab. 2. For MTBT no concentration resulted from the TPS.

451 **Tab. 2:** OMP average concentrations (C_w) obtained for a 7 day experiment of the mini-TPS in WWTP effluent
 452 calculated from time-dependent and load-dependent TPS calibration compared to mean concentrations from 7 day
 453 composite water samples.

Compound	C_w in $\mu\text{g/L}$					
	time-dependent ^a		load-dependent ^a		autosampler ^b	
Phenazone	0.23	± 0.01	0.21	± 0.01	0.33	± 0.01
AAA	2.8	± 0.2	2.8	± 0.2	3.0	± 0.2
AMPH	0.19	± 0.01	0.19	± 0.01	0.35	± 0.01
FAA	9.5	± 0.7	9.4	± 0.7	11.6	± 0.9
Diclofenac	3.8	± 0.3	3.8	± 0.3	4.0	± 0.3
Metoprolol	2.0	± 0.1	1.9	± 0.1	1.7	± 0.1
DEET	0.12	± 0.01	0.11	± 0.01	0.13	± 0.01
Benzotriazole	42.8	± 1	35.5	± 0.9	16.6	± 0.4
Tolyltriazole	11.5	± 0.1	10.1	± 0.1	7.9	± 0.1

454 ^a Calculated value ± absolute error, based on the individual error,

455 ^b Mean value ± absolute error, based on the individual error.

456 The OMP concentrations calculated via the load-dependent and time-dependent TPS
 457 calibration are ranging in two orders of magnitude from 0.11 $\mu\text{g/L}$, 0.12 $\mu\text{g/L}$,
 458 respectively for DEET and 35.5 $\mu\text{g/L}$, 42.8 $\mu\text{g/L}$, respectively for benzotriazole and are
 459 in similar ranges as concentrations obtained from auto-sampling. The values
 460 generated from the PS are mostly in good agreement with those from the autosampler,
 461 e.g. 3.8 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (load-dependent TPS) and 4.0 $\mu\text{g/L}$ (autosampler) for diclofenac.
 462 Deviations >30% occur for AMPH and benzotriazole, yet the TPS still allows for rough
 463 quantitative assessments for such OMPs. We further assume that more calibration
 464 data points and more routine in deployment of the mini-TPS will allow for increased
 465 accuracy. The concentrations derived from the time-dependent and the
 466 load-dependent calibrations are comparable, while both approaches likely profit from
 467 the overall highly constant conditions facilitated by the TPS. The TPS is a valuable
 468 asset for long-term monitoring of WWTP effluents where autosampling is often very

469 time- and resource-consuming. Another advantage of the TPS compared to
470 autosamplers is its small size, allowing for deployment in monitoring booths or running
471 process lines. This feature also means that temperatures below freezing impact the
472 TPS much less than autosamplers which malfunction easily due to freezing water in
473 intermittently ponding supply tubes; the constantly running water flow in the TPS
474 avoids malfunction by freezing. Due to its versatility of using any commercial 47 mm
475 SPE disc material, the TPS opens up many possibilities for monitoring chemically
476 variable target compounds while being integrated into the existing analytical
477 equipment.

478 4 Conclusion

479 This study tested a semi-passive sampler concept with precisely adjustable volumetric
480 flow, containing standard 47 mm SPE discs, to monitor organic micro-pollutants in
481 WWTP effluent. A miniaturized design with two passive sampler discs was
482 implemented in pressurized lines of a WWTP monitoring station. After a load-
483 dependent calibration of the system, an additional test run showed applicable and
484 determined average WWTP effluent concentrations for a variety of OMPs, which were
485 highly similar to concentrations obtained from measured composite samples. Given
486 the straightforward handling once installed, and – more importantly – the
487 good/accurate quantitative results, this semi-passive system is, to our knowledge, the
488 first to calibrate passive sampler discs with exact feed water loads of potentially
489 strongly fluctuating concentrations, combined with the possibility to operate in
490 pressurized lines. The load-dependent calibration and the time-dependent calibration
491 both agreed well with corresponding composite samples. Further experiments should
492 compare the load-dependent and time-dependent calibrations within the TPS with

493 “classical” passive sampling without volumetric flow control. Many use-cases appear
494 feasible for the TPS, like quantitative continuous monitoring which spares – once the
495 TPS is calibrated – the need for extensive and laborious auto-sampling. Due to the
496 versatility of the TPS, further application could result from continuous monitoring of
497 industrial discharges by either the industry themselves or authorities^{43,44}.

498 Supporting Information

499 Additional experimental details, materials, and methods, including photographs of
500 experimental setup

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